

A Study on Women Entrepreneur towards Work Life Balance, Prospects and Problems in India

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Abstract

Entrepreneurship has played a vital role in India. Entrepreneurship has a traditionally considered as favour of male gender. Despite, in connection with changing socio-cultural environment and an enhance in educational opportunities, women have began knowing their integral talents and business skills. This study revealed objectives was to develop and formalize a suitable tool to illustrate the work-life balance issues faced by rural women entrepreneurs. In this study the researcher was attempted to realize the significant factors affect the work life balance of women entrepreneurs inspite of, increased number of women participated in entrepreneurial tasks. This study tookover about that rural women entrepreneurs in India. Women entrepreneur has normally achieved in the goal setting, information seeking, and systematic planning and monitoring competencies. In this researcher has revealed that they were generally able to maintained work life balance through proper time management and strived to spend more time with family members together with their spouses and children. The aim of this study had examine the issues and problems of respective women entrepreneurship in rural area. This paper was based on secondary data and collected some reveals for the identification of these issues from different research articles and reports. This study revealed that role of excess, dependent care issues, quality of health, problems with time management and lack of proper social support. Those factors caused the work life balance of women entrepreneurs in India.

Keywords: Entrepreneurship, Women, Business, Gender, Prospects and problems

Introduction

In recent years women entrepreneur has developing in many domains such as industrialization, urbanization, social legislation. Women entrepreneur has been traced traditionally than exclusive male. In 1950s, women had focused only their family after 1960s women began to start small business enterprises at home and has been created self occupation. In women Entrepreneurial roles has increasingly and achieved their goals. Women often contributed in their father's or husband's business and equally succeeded. In 1990s The women entrepreneur has increased and learnt to live alone, travel alone and if required to feed their children alone even more

opportunities arise for women in 21st century. Women entrepreneurship has gained momentum in the last three decades with the increase in the number of women enterprises and their substantive contribution to economic growth Sharma (2013). Current entrepreneurs had creative thinking and the development of new ideas. At this occasion, it is worth mentioning that entrepreneurs are different from small-business owners. Have made it very clear that small business owners are primarily concerned with securing an income to meet their immediate needs, rather than engaging in innovation. In spite of female entrepreneurship increased rapid growth, the actual number of men who were conceived new businesses (Minniti & Bygrave, 2003). Women-owned businesses were, on average, smaller than those owned by men (Fischer, Reuber, & Dyke, 1993) However, the situation prevailing in developing and under developed nations is not as conducive to female entrepreneurship (Nawaser, 2010). A comprehensive survey of the literature shows that specific studies pertaining to the work life balance issues of women entrepreneurs were very few. The only available reports on the bring out, which was mainly from developing nations, stipulate that women entrepreneurs of these nations enjoyed work life balance (Key et al., 2003). (Khanka, 2010; Mann & Phukan, 2010; Anitha & Lakshmi, 1999) either focused on female emancipation the contributed of the few successful women entrepreneurs.

Objective of the Study

The study is based on secondary data which is collected from newspapers, journals, websites, etc. The study was planned to discuss the following objectives:

- To study the work life balance of women entrepreneur in India.
- To study the role rural women entrepreneurs in India.
- To examine the prospects and problems faced by women entrepreneurship in rural area.

Women Empowerment in India

Hazarika, (2011) Women in India enjoy a unique status of equality with the men as per constitutional and legal provision. But the Indian women have come a long way to achieve the present positions. Gender inequality in India can be traced back to the historic days of Mahabharata when Draupadi was put on the dice by her husband as a commodity. History has witnessed that women were made to across both in private and public places.

In the Indian society, a female was always dependent on male members of the family even last few years ago. A female was not allowed to speak with loud voice in the presence of elder members of her in laws. In the family, every fault had gone to her and responsible. As a widow her dependence on a male members of the family still more increased. In many social activities she was not permitted to mix with other members of the family. On the phase in political, social and economic life of the society. The early twenty century, it was rise of the National Movement under the leadership of Mahatma Gandhi who was in favor of removing all the disabilities of women. At the same time, Raja Ram Mohan Rai, Iswar Chandra Vidyasagar and various other social reformers laid stress on women's education, prevention of child marriage, withdrawal of evil practice of sati, removal of polygamy etc. Women Empowerment was basically the creation of an environment where women can make independent decisions about their personal development as well as shine as equals in society.

Dhruba, (2011) While the ancient India adhere great respect and importance to women, ironically, it was only in the modern India in spite of the technology revolution and higher literacy rate, the need for women empowerment is increasingly causing great concern. The recent times have seen an alarming rise in crimes against women. According to the National Crime Records Bureau, A total of 2,44,270 incidents of crime against women were reported in the country during the year

2012 as compared to 2,28,650 in the year 2011 recording an increase of 6.4% during the year 2012. These crimes have continuously increased during 2008 – 2012 to 1,95,856 cases in the year 2008, 2,03,804 cases in 2009 and 2,13,585 cases in 2010 and 2,28,650 cases in 2011 and 2,44,270 cases in the year 2012.

Problems and Prospects of Women Entrepreneur

Rocca et al., (2009) revealed that the women empower themselves through vocational training, employment opportunities and social groups need to consider the potential unintended consequences for these women, such as an increased risk of domestic violence. Researcher suggested that the effectiveness of anti-dowry laws may be limited without additional strategies that mobilize women, families and communities to challenge the widespread acceptance of dowry and to promote gender equity. Longitudinal studies are needed to elucidate the complex causal relationships between ‘love’ marriages and domestic violence. Donald, (2005) Entrepreneurship has emerged over the last two decades as arguably the most potent economic force the world had ever experienced. With that expansion has come a similar increased in the field of entrepreneurship education. The recent growth and development in the curricula and programs devoted to entrepreneurship and new venture creation have been remarkable. The number of colleges and universities that offer courses related to entrepreneurship has grown from a handful in the 1970s to over 1,600 in 2005. In the midst of this huge expansion remains the challenge of complete academic legitimacy for entrepreneurship. Goyal & Prakesh, (2011) The educated Indian women have to go a long way to achieve equal rights and position because traditions are deep rooted in Indian society where the sociological set up has been a male dominated one. Despite all the social hurdles, Indian women stand tall from the rest of the crowd and are applauded for their achievements in their respective field. The transformation of social fabric of the Indian society, in terms of increased educational status of women and varied aspirations for better living, necessitated a change in the life style of Indian women.

Women has competed with man and successfully stood up with him in every walk of life and business is no exception for this. These women leaders are assertive, persuasive and willing to take risks. They managed to survive and succeed in this cut throat competition with their hard work, diligence and perseverance. The role of Women entrepreneur in economic development is also being recognized and steps are being taken to promote women entrepreneurship. Resurgence of entrepreneurship is the need of the hour emphasizing on educating women strata of population, spreading awareness and consciousness amongst women to outshine in the enterprise field, making them realize their strengths, and important position in the society and the great contribution they can make for their industry as well as the entire economy.

Conclusion

This paper revealed that the women’s entrepreneurship has to determine underlying explanations for these gender-based differences and examines the long term implications for women entrepreneurs who want to start and grow their own businesses. This Study was suggested that the encouragement of rural women entrepreneurship was one of the ways for that But unfortunately that the traditional mind was set of the society and the negligenced of the state and respective authorities obstacles in the rural women entrepreneurship development in India. Apart from the responsibility of the state and society, absence of balance between family and career obligations of women, poor degree of financial freedom for rural women, absence of direct ownership of the property to rural women, inconsistency of entrepreneurial skill & finance in economically rich and poor women, no awareness about capacities, low ability to bear risks, problems of work with

male workers, negligence by financial institutions, lack of self confidence, lack of professional education, mobility constraints and lack of interaction with successful entrepreneurs are major problems of rural women entrepreneurship development in India.

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